

Title:

Note on the problem of considering the presence of wall in the modeling of chromatographic columns

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Abstract

The development of modern chromatography, in addition to improving and creating new experimental techniques, also includes the progress of precise and robust mathematical models and fast and reliable numerical methods enabling their solution. Accurate mathematical models combined with effective numerical techniques enable prediction of the behavior of chromatographic columns in various operating conditions. In a series of recent works Qamar et al. proposed a number of effective numerical solutions that provide profiles of concentrations and outlet temperatures also in non-isothermal conditions, requiring the application of a heat transport model in the chromatographic system modeling. However, to simplify the solutions, the authors did not take into account the presence of an important object for heat transport, which is the column wall. In our work a mathematical model of the column taking into account the presence of wall is proposed. The model is solved for a number of selected typical cases of chromatography for a variable conditions of: column diameter, solute inlet concentration, column wall material and thermal effects of the adsorption process. Based on the obtained results, the column operating conditions were indicated in which the neglecting of the column wall presence is acceptable (analytical conditions) and column wall presence in the model cannot be omitted.

Highlights

1. Precise mathematical models enable prediction of HPLC column operation
2. Presence of column walls impacts heat transfer and temperature distribution

3. Presence of walls can be neglected for HPLC and low solute concentration
4. In other cases, column walls have to be considered in modeling

Keywords: HPLC column modeling, column walls effects, analytical conditions, preparative conditions

1. Introduction

Effective prediction of solute concentration profiles requires selecting and solving an appropriate mathematical model of the chromatographic retention process. In the case of a process conducted under analytical conditions at mild flowrates, a mathematical model that takes into account only the mass balance is sufficient and can be effectively applied without the risk of making significant mistakes. However, progressive development of chromatographic techniques related to the shift towards smaller packing bed particles, higher throughputs and higher inlet pressures means that the assumption of the isothermal conditions may bring about serious errors during modeling and can no longer be accepted. The most common cases where evident non-isothermality cannot be ignored include: **(a)** relatively high flow rates of the mobile phase and/or columns packed with sub-2- μm particles are applied causing high inlet pressures and a significant pressure drops along the column; **(b)** the fluid used as the mobile phase is in supercritical conditions, especially near the critical point (Supercritical Fluid Chromatography, SFC); **(c)** the adsorption process is highly exothermic with substantial heat release what is also the subject of our interest in this paper.

Since liquid chromatography can be divided into High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) when inlet pressure is less than about 400 bar and Ultra High Performance Liquid Chromatography (UHPLC) for back pressures exceeding 400 bar the case mentioned in point **(a)** regards mainly the retention models in the UHPLC regime. For successful modeling, it is indispensable to introduce appropriate heat transport equations to complete the mass balance, defining the amount of heat released due to viscous friction per unit volume of a column [1,2]. The heat released in such cases is responsible for formation of gradients of crucial physicochemical quantities (radial and axial temperature gradients play a special role here), and thus a change in the retention time, a change in the shape of the peak, and even a peak split, what was discussed in papers [2–5]. It should be emphasized that the gradients are also influenced by the column wall, its thickness and thermal conductivity coefficient. Since the column wall is made

of stainless steel changes in the peak shapes can significantly affect the number of theoretical plates. Advanced simulations of temperature distribution in columns, taking into account the presence of steel column walls and confirming their importance in heat transport were presented in the articles [6,7].

In the case **(b)** concerning SFC chromatography, the non-isothermal nature of the process results from the expansion of the supercritical fluid flowing through the column due to the pressure drop between the inlet and outlet. The expanding mobile phase absorbs heat from the environment and causes local cooling of the system, and consequently the formation of axial and radial temperature gradients [8,9]. As a result, similarly to the point **(a)**, an effective mathematical model describing the process has to take into account the heat transport involving the heat conduction in the column walls, in the form of a term: $(1 - \alpha T)u\nabla P$ (see Eq. (1)).

In chromatographic separations, as a rule, the concentration of analytes is so low that the heat of adsorption practically does not affect local temperatures inside the column and usually is not taken into account during modeling. However, when a large mass and concentration of the solute is introduced into the column, and the heat of adsorption is very high, then, as shown in papers by Qamar et al. [10] and by Khan et al. [11], the calculated chromatographic peak profiles can be significantly different from those obtained for the analytical conditions when heat of adsorption is close to zero. The authors of these studies assumed that the column is operated in adiabatic conditions, which in reality is practically not the case, since chromatographic separations usually are performed under natural or forced convection conditions in a closed air chamber or in a water-cooled jacket. Unfortunately, in their theoretical model the authors also omitted the presence of column walls in heat distribution process. Referring to the solutions used in practice, chromatographic columns are mainly made of stainless steel of outstanding thermal conductivity (about $16 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ comparing to $1.4 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ for pure silica), therefore their contribution to the transport of heat generated inside the column cannot be ignored. In typical cases of columns operating under natural convection conditions, heat generated by viscous friction within the packing warms up the walls at the column outlet and is then conducted along the column walls towards the cooler column inlet [4,5]. As a result, one can expect that the contribution of the columns to the temperature distribution inside the column is as significant as in the case of points **(a)** and **(b)**.

The aim of this paper is to perform theoretical calculations involving mathematical modeling of chromatographic columns as close as possible to real experimental conditions, however involving cases of pronounced values of adsorption enthalpy, and then to analyze the effects of the process conditions on the concentration profiles at the

column outlet. Theoretical calculations include a number of different cases of chromatographic process implementation, each time taking into account the presence of column walls. The presented results are a complement and extension of the solutions presented in the series of works by Qamar et. al [10–13] and also their adaptation to more realistic experimental conditions. The authors of [10–13], using recognized mathematical models and advanced numerical methods for solving partial differential equations, proved the significant influence of thermal effects on the solute concentration profiles at the column outlet, under various process conditions. However, their approach requires supplementation, in which the presence of chromatographic column walls should be also taken into account. Column walls are an inseparable element of the chromatographic system operated under high pressure. The practical cases of a chromatographic column analyzed in this work include: **(i)** the presence of column walls made of materials with different thermal conductivity (i.e. made of stainless steel and polyether ether ketone, PEEK), **(ii)** various cases of heat release out of a column operated in adiabatic conditions, under near perfect insulation conditions (high vacuum), in natural heat convection (air chamber) and in forced heat convection (water jacket); **(iii)** different internal column diameters (including the most commonly used in practice: 2.1 mm, 4.6 mm and 10 mm), **(iv)** different levels of solute inlet concentration (0.01, 0.1 and 1 mol·m⁻³); and **(v)** different levels of a solute adsorption enthalpy (between 0 and -60 kJ·mol⁻¹).

2. Theory

As described in several papers [1-17], prediction of concentration profiles at the outlet of a chromatographic column operating in real non-isothermal conditions requires a combination of column heat balance model, mass balance model and momentum balance model. Their proper application can provide information on the spatio-temporal distributions of temperature and pressure in the system under consideration and, consequently, allows to find the distribution of local fluid velocity as well as the distributions of crucial physicochemical properties of the system. As a result, it is possible to calculate the concentration profiles at the column outlet consistent with the experimental data.

A chromatographic column can be approximated by a cylindrical tube filled with adsorbent as shown in Fig. 1. The heat balance model incorporates heat transfer within the cylindrical tube and porous column packing immersed in mobile phase, whereas mass and momentum balance models refer to space occupied by column packing.

Figure 1. Chromatographic column cross-section

The details of the applied mathematical approach involving the mentioned heat, mass and momentum balances are presented in the following sections.

2.1. Heat balance model

The heat balance model involves separate equations for column packing bed consisting of stationary phase and interstitial liquid, Eq. (1), and for column wall, Eq. (2). The chromatographic column is described by its basic geometry: internal radius R_{in} [m], external radius R_{out} [m], and length L [m]. Due to column symmetry the equations are expressed as follows using cylindrical coordinates:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (\varepsilon_t C_{P,m} + (1 - \varepsilon_t) C_{P,s}) \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \varepsilon_t T \alpha \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} + C_{P,m} u_x \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + C_{P,m} u_r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \lambda_{eff} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\lambda_{eff} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) - \\
 & (1 - \varepsilon_t) \sum_{i=1}^{NC} (\Delta H_i) \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial t} - u_x (1 - \alpha T) \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} - u_r (1 - \alpha T) \frac{\partial P}{\partial r}
 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$C_{P,w} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\lambda_w}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \lambda_w \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} \quad (2)$$

where $C_{P,m}$, $C_{P,s}$ and $C_{P,w}$, are the heat capacities of mobile phase, stationary phase, and column wall [$\text{J} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$], respectively, ε_t is the total porosity of the stationary phase, α is the mobile phase thermal expansion coefficient [K^{-1}], u_x is the mobile phase superficial velocity in the axial direction (x) [$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$], u_r is the mobile phase superficial velocity in the radial direction (r) [$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$], λ_{eff} is the effective conductivity of the stationary phase [$\text{W} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$], λ_w is the wall thermal conductivity [$\text{W} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$], ΔH_i is the adsorption enthalpy of the i -th component, NC represents number of components, P is the local pressure [Pa] and T is the local temperature [K]. In this approach we assumed that the adsorption of modifier can be neglected.

The total bed porosity ε_t and the mobile phase thermal expansion coefficient α is can be calculated from Eq. (S1) and Eq. (S2), respectively. The effective thermal conductivity (λ_{eff}) of the solid porous bed immersed in the eluent (in Eq. (1)) was calculated according to Zarichnyak [18] using Eq. (S3).

The heat balance equations (1) and (2) have to be coupled with the following initial and boundary conditions. At time $t = 0$ temperature of a column (both bed and wall) is assumed constant:

$$\text{for } t = 0 \quad T(t, x, r) = \text{const} \quad (3)$$

At the external surface of the column wall, the following conditions are assumed:

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = R_{out} \quad -\lambda_w \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} = h_{ext}(T - T_{ext}) \quad (4)$$

while within the column walls:

$$\text{for } t > 0, R_{in} > r > R_{out}, x = 0 \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{for } t > 0, R_{in} > r > R_{out}, x = L \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (6)$$

where T_{ext} is the temperature [K] of the fluid surrounding the column and h_{ext} is the external heat transfer coefficient [$\text{W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{K}^{-1}$] dependent on the thermal conditions of the column operation.

As can be seen in Fig. 1, the proposed model does not explicitly consider the column heads. In general, column heads are massive objects that actively participate in heat exchange with the environment, but their shape and size depend on the solutions used by different manufacturers. However, as shown in [17], the correct temperature and pressure profiles in the chromatographic column can be obtained by omitting the presence of heads in the heat balance, using a correctly estimated apparent heat transfer coefficient. Moreover, in recent years, a clear trend in the reduction of the head sizes can be observed, and their outer diameter differs only slightly in relation to the outer diameter of the column.

At the boundary between the column packing bed and the wall, the conditions of heat flux continuity and of temperature continuity are required:

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = R_{in} \quad \lambda_w \frac{\partial T(r=R_{in}^-)}{\partial r} = \lambda_{eff} \frac{\partial T(r=R_{in}^+)}{\partial r} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{and} \quad T(r = R_{in}^-) = T(r = R_{in}^+) \quad (8)$$

At the center of the column, a symmetry condition was applied:

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = 0 \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} = 0 \quad (9)$$

At the inlet to the column packing bed constant temperature T_{in} of a mobile phase was assumed:

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = 0, r < R_{in} \quad T(r, x = 0) = T_{in} \quad (10)$$

while at the column packing bed outlet:

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = L, r < R_{in} \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (11)$$

2.2 Momentum balance model

As already proposed and proven in previous papers [4,14–16,19,20] the equation describing local pressure distribution in a column is as follows:

$$\varepsilon_t \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial P} \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \right) - \text{div} \left(\rho \cdot \frac{\kappa}{\eta} \text{grad}(P) \right) = 0 \quad (12)$$

Eq (12) was created by a combination of the continuity equation (Eq.(S4)) with Darcy's law (Eq.(S5)) that enables to calculate the superficial velocity of the mobile phase knowing the gradient of pressure.

In order to solve numerically the momentum balance equation (Eq. (12)) the following initial (Eq.(13)) and boundary (Eqs. (14) - (17)) conditions have to be accepted:

$$\text{for } t = 0 \quad P = P_0 \quad (13)$$

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = R_{in} \quad \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} = 0 \quad (14)$$

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = 0 \quad \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = 0, r < R_{in} \quad P(r, x = 0) = P_0 \quad (16)$$

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = L, r < R_{in} \quad P(r, x = L) = P_{out} \quad (17)$$

The solution of the model (Eq. (12)) has to satisfy the boundary conditions, i.e., for example, imposing the flow rate should result in the inlet pressure fixed at the assumed value (P_0). Unfortunately, the P_0 value is usually unknown and must be calculated beforehand, which comes down to calculating the steady state of the solution. This first stage of calculations (E1) is analogous to the real experimental conditioning of the column before starting the actual study, which can be called the second stage (E2). After reaching the steady state, the solute is injected into the column and the calculations of the stage E2 begin. The final distribution of T and P and the concentration of the solute over time should be corrected for the time of the end of stage E1.

The average mass flow rate $(u_x \rho)_{av}$ in any cross-section of a column can be assumed constant. Consequently, also at the column inlet, where fluid local velocity in x direction is u_{x0} and local fluid density is ρ_0 :

$$(u_x \rho)_{av} = const = u_{x0} \rho_0 \quad (18)$$

Applying the Darcy's law (Eq. (S5)) one can obtain:

$$u_{x0} \rho_0 = -\rho_0 \frac{\kappa}{\eta} \frac{dP}{dx} \quad (19)$$

As a result the boundary condition at the column inlet can be formulated:

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = 0 \quad u_{x0} \rho_0 = -\rho_0 \frac{\kappa}{\eta_0} \frac{dP}{dx} \Big|_{x=0} \quad (20)$$

Another boundary condition is the constant pressure P_{out} at the column outlet:

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = L \quad P = P_{out} \quad (21)$$

2.3 Mass balance model

A relatively simple mathematical model that allows describing the chromatography process for one component with required accuracy is the equilibrium-dispersive model (ED) that assumes the solute concentrations in the mobile and stationary phases to be in local equilibrium and accounts for the finite mass transfer between the phases through the apparent axial and radial dispersion coefficients. The two-dimensional ED model in cylindrical coordinates is expressed as follows [4,5,14,15,17,21]:

$$\frac{\partial c_i}{\partial t} + \frac{(1-\varepsilon_t)}{\varepsilon_t} \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{\varepsilon_t} \text{div}(c_i \cdot \mathbf{u}) = \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial x} \left(D_{ai,x} \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial r} \left(r D_{ai,r} \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial r} \right) \quad (22)$$

where c_i [mol·m⁻³] and q_i [mol·m⁻³] are i -th solute concentrations in the mobile and the stationary phases, respectively, while $D_{ai,x}$ and $D_{ai,r}$ are the apparent axial and the radial dispersion coefficients [m²·s⁻¹] of the i -th solute, respectively.

In order to account for temperature effects on the adsorption process the following Langmuir type model with temperature effect was considered:

$$q_i = \frac{q_0 K_i c_i}{1 + \sum_{i=1}^{NC} K_i c_i} \quad (23)$$

where q_0 [mol·m⁻³], K_i [m³·mol⁻¹] are the isotherm parameters, and parameter K_i is defined as:

$$K_i = K_{0i} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta H_i}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_{in}}\right)\right) \quad (24)$$

where K_{0i} [$\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$] is the isotherm parameter of i -th solute, ΔH_i is the enthalpy of adsorption of i -th solute [J mol^{-1}], and R is the universal gas constant [$\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$].

The apparent axial dispersion coefficient $D_{ai,x}$ in the ED model (Eq. (22)) can be calculated from the equation Eq. (S10) given in [14,15,21]. The radial dispersion coefficient, $D_{ai,r}$, (Eq. (22)) can be found applying the equation Eq. (S14) derived by Knox et al. [22].

In this work, values of all required fluid parameters depending on temperature and pressure were obtained from REFPROP by NIST (<https://www.nist.gov/srd/refprop>) or data available in Dortmund Data Bank (<http://www.ddbst.com/ddb.html>) at each collocation point and integration time.

In order to solve the mass balance model (Eq.(22)) the Danckwerts boundary conditions [23] were applied with the following details:

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = 0 \quad u(c_F - c) = \varepsilon_t D_a \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} \quad (25)$$

with:

$$c_F = \begin{cases} c_0 & \text{for } t \in (0, t_{inj}) \\ 0 & \text{for } t > t_{inj} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

and

$$\text{for } t > 0, x = L \quad \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (27)$$

where c_0 is the solute injection concentration [$\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$]-and t_{inj} is the solute injection time [s].

Additionally, the following initial and boundary conditions are required to solve the mass balance model:

$$\text{for } t = 0 \quad c(x, r) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad q(x, r) = 0 \quad (28)$$

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = 0 \quad \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (29)$$

$$\text{for } t > 0, r = R_{int} \quad \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (30)$$

Very similar model was previously verified and allowed to successfully predict concentration profiles in temperature gradient chromatography conditions [16] as well as in overloaded UHPLC conditions [17].

3. Numerical methods

3.1. Calculations details

Achieving satisfactory results of the column operation modeling requires simultaneous solution of a system of partial differential equations (PDE) (Eq.(1), Eq.(2), Eq.(21) and Eq.(29)), what is only possible using numerical methods. One of the most effective numerical techniques for solving PDE is the method of lines in which the spatial derivatives are approximated with finite difference scheme. As a result, the PDE set is replaced by a set of ordinal differential equations (ODE) since the time derivatives of unknown functions can be expressed by algebraic equations. Then, the ODE set can be solved with an appropriate ODE solver. One of the most robust numerical approaches, also applied in this work, is the orthogonal collocation on finite elements (OCFE) algorithm for approximation of the spatial derivatives in the ODE [23]. Following this algorithm, the column model domain (2D space is sufficient due to column symmetry) was divided into subdomains (referred to as finite elements) along and across the column axis. In each subdomain, number of internal collocation points (NICP) are selected as the roots of the NICP-th order Legendre polynomial as described in detail in [24]. The number of subdomains as well as number of collocation points were set so that their further increase did not affect the obtained solution. The details of the applied spatial discretization are given in Table S1 (Supplementary material).

The set of ODEs obtained after discretization was solved using the CVODE solver available in the SUNDIALS package provided by Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, USA [25]. The CVODE solver with the backward differentiation formula (BDF) method was selected because it is dedicated for solving stiff problems with sharp discontinuities among which is also the chromatographic column model [17]. In this work, calculations were performed setting the relative and absolute errors to be equal to 10^{-6} and 10^{-8} , respectively. The computations were done on workstation equipped with CPU - AMD Ryzen; Threadripper PRO 3975WX, (32 cores) 8 x 32 GB RAM, 2x2 TB SDD, working under MS Windows 11. The parameters' values used for simulations are presented in the Table 2 S2 (Supplementary material). Solute-specific parameters were adapted as for phenol.

3.2. Numerical experiment details

The paper presents a series of results of numerical calculations performed for various cases of chromatographic column operation, both for typical analytical conditions and for selected preparative cases. In order to distinguish the investigated and discussed cases of calculations, the case symbols presented in Table 3 1 were used. In order to make it easier to link a given calculation case with the obtained solution, an appropriate symbol identifying the given case was added to the result graphs (in the upper right corner).

Table 1. Summary of numerical calculation cases

Column wall material	Column inner diameter d_{in} [mm]	Inlet concentration c_0 [mol·m ⁻³]	Case symbol
Stainless steel	2.1	0.01	S21-C10
		0.1	S21-C100
		1.0	S21-C1000
	4.6	1.0	S46-C1000
	10.0	1.0	S100-C1000
PEEK	2.1	0.01	P21-C10
		0.1	P21-C100
		1.0	P21-C1000
	4.6	1.0	P46-C1000
	10.0	1.0	P100-C1000

3.3. Theoretical model verification

Prior to the numerical calculations taking into account different cases of the chromatographic process, the mathematical model presented in Section 2 was verified against the solution obtained by Khan et al. in [11]. The authors of [11] solved the non-isothermal lumped kinetic model (LK) of a chromatographic column involving bi-Langmuir adsorption model by application of high resolution finite volume (HR-FVS) numerical scheme given by Koren [26]. It should be noted that the proposed equilibrium dispersive (ED) model of mass transfer inherently assumes that the mass transfer resistances are taken into account via the apparent mass dispersion coefficients $D_{a,x}$

and $D_{a,r}$ (Eq. (28)). Therefore, the solution obtained in [11] for the case of the LK model with mass-transfer rate coefficient $k = 100 \text{ min}^{-1}$ was chosen to verify the model proposed here. It should be noted that for k increasing to infinity the solution of the ED model is identical to the LK model. The verification case concerns a 100 mm long column operating in adiabatic conditions, with a constant fluid interstitial velocity of $1 \text{ cm} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ and with the assumption of adsorption heat equal to $-20 \text{ kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$. For the remaining details of the case, the reader is referred to the paper [11].

Figure 2. Comparison of concentration profiles obtained by solution of the proposed model (ED model solved with OCFE) and by solution the model proposed by Khan et al. [11] solved with HR-FVS method

As can be seen in Fig. 2, the solution calculated based on the proposed column model (solid red line) is in good accordance with the solution obtained by Khan et al. [11] (dash-dotted blue line). Small discrepancies result from differences in the solutions of equilibrium (ED) and non-equilibrium (LK) models applied in both solutions, however it can be concluded that both models provide equivalent results.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Analytical stainless steel and PEEK columns in analytical conditions

In the first approach, we decided to present the results of the simulation of the chromatographic columns used in analytical conditions, i.e. with dimensions of 2.1 mm (ID) x 8 mm (OD) x 100 mm (length), loaded with a low concentration of the solute ($c_0 = 0.01 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$). The calculations were repeated for columns with walls made of stainless steel and PEEK to check how the thermal conductivity of the wall material ($\lambda_{wS} = 16 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for stainless steel and $\lambda_{wP} = 0.25 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for PEEK, respectively) affects the obtained results. Both columns were assumed to be packed with 5 μm silica particles. The assumed superficial inlet velocity of water u_{x0} , which was the eluent, was $0.001 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, that corresponds to the flow rate of $1 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The injection time t_{inj} was set to 30 s, while the enthalpy of adsorption ΔH was accepted equal to $-60 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ (cases S21-C10 and P21-C10). The remaining parameters adopted during the simulation are listed in Table S2 (Supplementary material). In order to facilitate the comparison of the inlet concentration effects, the relative concentration (c/c_0) is used in the plots, which is related to the initial solute concentration c_0 . In addition, in each plot three data instances are collected representing the column operated under three different thermal conditions: almost perfect insulation ($h_{ext} = 0.001 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$), natural convection in the air ($h_{ext} = 10 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$), and forced convection in water jacket ($h_{ext} = 1000 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$). Moreover, to contrast the mentioned real cases, the graphs also include theoretical adiabatic conditions in which the column has no physical walls and no heat exchange with the environment occurs.

Figure 3. Simulation results obtained for chromatographic columns operated under analytical conditions with inlet solute concentration $c_0 = 0.01 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$: a) concentration profile in 2.1 mm stainless steel column, b) outlet temperature profile in 2.1 mm stainless steel column, c) concentration profile in 2.1 mm PEEK column, d) outlet temperature profile in 2.1 mm PEEK column

Figure 3 shows the concentration and temperature profiles at the column outlet for the cases described above (cases S21-C10 and P21-C10). As can be seen, under analytical conditions, the actual columns behavior is almost identical to the theoretical column under adiabatic conditions. The concentration profiles (Fig. 3a and 3c) for both columns almost completely overlap, and the differences are practically imperceptible. This is due to very small fluctuations in the outlet temperature. In the case of adiabatic conditions (red line), the small temperature increase (not exceeding 0.2 K) associated with the release of heat during the solute adsorption is followed by the temperature drop (by about 0.2 K) caused by the solute desorption. This phenomenon is associated with the fact that the released heat is dissipated only with the fluid stream leaving the column.

In the real instances the column walls participate in the heat transport. As a result, the outlet temperature of the steel column is practically constant and equal to the inlet temperature (Fig. 3b). In the case of the PEEK column, with 64 times lower thermal conductivity of wall material, a slight increase in temperature can be observed due to the insufficient dissipation of adsorption heat to the environment (Fig. 3d).

To summarize, in the case of analytical columns with inner diameter of 2.1 mm, operating under low concentration conditions, the real column model can be successfully replaced by a theoretical model of an adiabatic column with no walls, and neglecting the presence of walls does not induce errors of practical significance. This statement is valid not only for low concentration conditions, but also for low pressure drops with low viscous heating. It is to be expected that for large pressure drops caused by high flow rates omitting the column wall will also result in larger errors.

Analytical stainless steel and PEEK columns in preparative conditions

In the next step, the behavior of 2.1 mm diameter columns was re-examined under preparative conditions, i.e. with the inlet concentration of the solute increased 10 times ($c_0 = 0.1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, Fig. S2 in Supplementary material, cases S21-C100 and P21-C100) and 100 times ($c_0 = 1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, case S21-C1000 in Fig. 4 and case P21-C1000 in Fig. S3 in Supplementary material) comparing to the case in previous section. The fact that the column wall can be made of

stainless steel or PEEK was again taken into account. Apart from the inlet concentration, the remaining parameters of the columns and the process remained unchanged.

Ten times greater mass introduced into the column causes significant changes in the behavior of the system (see Fig. S2 in Supplementary material). The heat released due to adsorption increases the outlet temperature of the column operating in the adiabatic regime by approximately 1.85 K, after which the temperature drops 1.8 K below the initial temperature (Fig. S2 b and S2 d). The column walls are not able to effectively dissipate the amount of generated heat, which makes the temperature jump noticeable also in the case of columns operating in real conditions. The temperature perturbation transfer rate inside a substance is characterized by its thermal diffusivity which equals to the ratio of thermal conductivity to the product of specific heat capacity and density. In the studied cases the thermal diffusivity is equal $4.1 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ for stainless steel and $1.44 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ for PEEK, respectively. Thus, the temperature wave travels faster in steel compared to PEEK walls. In the steel column, only a small increase in outlet temperature is noticeable, reaching approximately 0.25 K in the case of full insulation and natural convection and about 0.2 K in the case of forced convection (Fig. S2 b). In the PEEK column case, the outlet temperature increase reaches approximately 0.75 K (Fig. S2 d), regardless of the heat removal mechanism applied.

Temperature fluctuations are the cause of differences in the shape of concentration profiles. The decrease in fluid temperature due to desorption in a column operating in the adiabatic regime (for t_r between 140 – 160 s) brings about the increase in local fluid viscosity and density, and finally decrease in local velocity u (see Eq. 15 - 17) and a slight increase in peak retention time t_r (ca. 10-12 s). The increase in retention time may, to some extent, follow from stronger adsorption in lower temperatures.

Figure 4. Simulation results obtained for chromatographic columns operated under analytical conditions with inlet solute concentration $c_0 = 1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$: a) concentration profile in 2.1 mm stainless steel column, b) outlet temperature profile in 2.1 mm stainless steel column

Further increase of inlet concentration to $c_0 = 1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ deepens phenomena observed at lower concentrations (Fig. 4 and Fig. S3 in Supplementary material). In the case of a column operating in adiabatic conditions, the jump of fluid temperature exceeds 20 K and reaches almost 344 K, after which the temperature drops to 315 K due to desorption. Rapid temperature changes result in atypical concentration profile. The outlet solute concentration initially increases to $c/c_0 = 0.3$, then decreases due to the temperature growth to approximately $c/c_0 = 0.2$, followed by equilibrium change and adsorption enhancement, and then increases again, reaching maximum ($c/c_0 = 0.46$) at approx. 140 s. The presence of column walls in the other considered temperature regimes mitigates the effects of rapid temperature fluctuations. However, the effect of thermal conductivity of the wall is important here again. While in the steel column the temperature increment reaches approx. 2 K, in the case of better heat insulating PEEK material the temperature surge is more pronounced, reaching 5 K. Generally, the shape of concentration profile features typical mass overload conditions with distinct peak tailing. While the heat removal mechanism again does not significantly differentiate the concentration profiles, the lower conductivity of the PEEK column walls causes more pronounced dispersion and peak deformation (the peak width at the baseline is about 20 s larger in the PEEK column comparing to the steel column, Figs. 4 a and S3 a). The effects of heat transport through walls with different thermal diffusivity coefficients are illustrated in Fig. 5 a and Fig. 5 b. As can be seen, the heat is dissipated quickly through the steel wall and clearly slower through the PEEK wall, which consequently leads to a higher temperature at the PEEK column outlet compared to the steel column.

Figure 5. Temperature distributions inside 2.1 x 100 mm chromatographic columns with inlet solute concentration $c_0 = 1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$: a) stainless steel column, b) PEEK column

In summary, the increase in inlet concentration c_0 to high levels typical for preparative conditions means that the presence of walls cannot be neglected in the creation of a mathematical model of the chromatographic separation process, even in the case of small, 2.1 mm columns. Moreover, the higher the concentration values and the higher the adsorption enthalpy values, the greater the discrepancies to be expected between a column operating under ideal adiabatic conditions and a real column equipped with physical external walls with specific thermal properties.

4.2 Preparative column in preparative conditions

The next step in the simulations was to investigate the effect of the presence of column walls made of stainless steel and PEEK in models of chromatographic columns with much larger cross-sections comparing to typical analytical columns, loaded with the highest considered inlet concentration $c_0 = 1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ of a solute. Columns of dimensions 4.6 mm (ID) x 8 mm (OD) x 100 mm (length) and 10.0 (ID) x 12.7 mm (OD) x 100 mm (length) were examined (cases S46-C1000, S100-1000, P46-C1000, P100-C1000). Apart from the inner diameters, other operating parameters of the system listed in Table S2 were left unchanged. However, due to the demand of maintaining constant superficial fluid

velocity of 0.001 m/s, the volumetric flow rate in the 4.6 mm ID column was increased to the level of 1 ml·min⁻¹, while in the 10.0 mm ID column to the level of 4.71 ml·min⁻¹, respectively.

Figure 6. Simulation results obtained for chromatographic column operated under preparative conditions with inlet solute concentration $c_0 = 1 \text{ mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$: a) concentration profile in 4.6 mm stainless steel column, b) outlet temperature profile in 4.6 mm stainless steel column, c) concentration profile in 4.6 mm PEEK column, d) outlet temperature profile in 4.6 mm PEEK column

Figure 7. Simulation results obtained for chromatographic column operated under preparative conditions with inlet solute concentration $c_0 = 1 \text{ mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$: a) concentration profile in 10 mm stainless steel column, b) outlet temperature profile in 10 mm stainless steel column, c) concentration profile in 10 mm PEEK column, d) outlet temperature profile in 10 mm PEEK column

As can be seen in Fig. 6 and 7, as well as in S4 and S5 in Supplementary material, the solution of the ideal adiabatic column model differs significantly from the solutions of the mathematical model taking into account the presence of a column wall and assuming significant heat dissipation due to radial heat transfer. In the case of both considered column diameters, the adiabatic model predicts significant temperature increase from the initial 323 K to over 353 K at t_r equal about 80 s, and then a decrease to 315 K above $t_r = 125$ s. The observed temperature changes, analogous

to those obtained for the previously analyzed cases, confirm that the outlet temperature depends only on the amount of the solute mass and the solute inlet concentration introduced into the adiabatic chromatographic system. Therefore, the concentration profiles observed at the column outlet also do not depend on the column size, but only on the mass and the inlet concentration of the solute injected into the column. On the other hand, introducing walls with real specific thermal properties to the model and adopting a selected heat transport mechanism significantly changes the course of temperature profiles followed by changes of concentration curves. The concentration and temperature profiles observed in the case of a 10 mm diameter PEEK column are particularly interesting (Fig. S5 a and S5 b). The limited thermal conductivity of the PEEK walls does not allow for effective removal of heat generated in the adsorption process, which causes characteristic deformations of the concentration peak with more than one apex. Also, the efficiency of heat dissipation outside the column (when the interior of the column is warmer than the surroundings) and heat absorption by the column (when the interior of the column cools down due to desorption) causes fluctuations in the intensity of mass transport towards the column outlet, which affects peak shape that may significantly differ from the expected triangular one.

Summarizing, in the case of preparative conditions, it is definitely recommended to consider the column walls presence in the robust model predicting its functioning. The model should incorporate the thermal parameters of the material structuring the walls as well as the appropriate heat transport mechanism especially when the environmental conditions can change and affect the thermal conditions during the operation of a chromatographic system.

4.3 Effects of adsorption enthalpy on preparative column performance

Since the issue of adsorption enthalpy appears to be of great importance in the conducted research, and in all previous results a constant value of this parameter was assumed, in the next point of the work it was checked how the value of adsorption enthalpy affects the obtained results. For this purpose, one of the examined cases from the preparative range was selected and calculations were repeated for different values of adsorption enthalpy, i.e. $\Delta H = 0, -10, -20, -40$ and $-60 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, and as well as for different column thermal conditions. The arbitrary choice was a steel column with dimensions of 4.6 mm (ID) x 8 mm (OD) x 10 mm (L), into which the solute was injected at concentration of $1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. The remaining column and process parameters were assumed in accordance with Table S2 (Supplementary material).

Figure 8. Simulation results obtained for 4.6 mm chromatographic column and inlet solute concentration $c_0 = 1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$: a) concentration profiles under adiabatic conditions, b) outlet temperature profile under adiabatic conditions, c) concentration profiles for $h_{ext} = 1000 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$, d) outlet temperature profile for $h_{ext} = 1000 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$

As expected, the more pronounced thermal effect of the adsorption process, the more evident the temperature fluctuations in the analyzed chromatographic system. Temperature growths caused by the emission of the adsorption heat, followed by less pronounced temperature decreases due to the desorption effects, are attenuated in the case of column models involving walls, which are clearly more efficient in heat dissipation processes (Fig. 8 and Fig S6). In such cases, the shape of the concentration peaks is classical, and its deformations result mainly from the overloaded inlet concentration. In turn, as stated earlier, an ideal column operating in the adiabatic regime accumulates heat generated during the solute adsorption-desorption process. As a result, sharp temperature fronts are formed in the column, which are responsible for the deformation of the peaks at the column outlet.

To summarize, the higher the heat effects of the adsorption process and subsequent desorption of a solute, the more significant temperature fluctuations should be expected in the chromatographic system and taking into account the presence of wall in the mathematical model in such cases is necessary for effective prediction of the process results.

4.4 Wall effects in a two-component chromatographic system

In order to supplement the results presented in previous sections the selected cases of elution profiles in a two-component system were also analyzed. The mathematical model describing such a case requires the introduction of another mass transport equation (Eq. (22)) for the second component, which in turn enforces the definition of the equation parameters and the details of adsorption equilibrium in a two-component system (Eqs. (23) and (24)). The case of a 4.6 mm (ID) \times 8 mm (OD) \times 100 mm (L) stainless steel column operating under near perfect insulation conditions ($h_{ext} = 0.001 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$) was selected for comparison with an analogous instance operated under adiabatic conditions (without column walls). The calculations assumed two solutes with a significant adsorption enthalpy value of $\Delta H = -60 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, however in order to make the heat release analogous to the previously discussed cases, the inlet concentrations c_{0i} of both solutes were reduced to $0.5 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. The column operating parameters remained identical to those in Table S2, while the data introduced in order to accomplish the two-component case are in detail listed in Table S3 placed in Supplementary material.

The elution curves of both components and the outlet temperature values as function of retention time are presented in Fig. 9. The isotherm parameters were selected so that the residence times of both solutes were similar, which allows to trace the effects of almost parallel adsorption and desorption processes of the components.

Figure 9. Simulation results obtained for 4.6 mm chromatographic column injected with a mixture of two solutes of identical inlet concentration $c_0 = 0.5 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$: a) concentration profiles under adiabatic conditions, b) concentration profiles for $h_{ext} = 0.001 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$

The issue of heat removal from the system is again crucial for the shape of the concentration profiles at the column outlet. The heat generated due to the solutes adsorption process under the adiabatic regime causes a strong temperature jump, reaching almost 20 K at $t_r \approx 90 \text{ s}$ (Fig. S7 a). Then the outlet temperature drops rapidly by over 25 K (minimum $T = 314.7 \text{ K}$ at $t_r \approx 150 \text{ s}$) due to the removal of heat from the fluid as a result of the desorption of solutes, and finally temperature levels off to values close to the inlet temperature ($T \approx 323 \text{ K}$). Such significant

temperature fluctuations in the system are reflected in the shape of the concentration profiles of both components. As a result of the dissipation of the heat of adsorption in the fluid, the local temperature of the fluid and the stationary phase initially increases. The adsorption equilibrium in the system is shifted, and the local fluid viscosity and velocity also increase with temperature. Then, due to rapid system cooling, the reverse processes take place, which ultimately results in strongly deformed elution curves of both components with very close retention times (Fig. 9 a). For comparison with the ideal adiabatic case, a system with almost perfect thermal insulation (corresponding to placing the column in a high vacuum) was selected. Despite these apparently similar thermal conditions, the calculation results differ significantly (Fig. 9b and Fig. S7 b). The reason lies in the presence of the stainless steel wall, which is responsible for the distribution of heat in the system, even in the case when, due to effective insulation, both heat emission to the environment and heat absorption from the environment are practically eliminated. In real conditions, which take into account the presence of a wall, the outlet temperature increase reaches about 326.6 K at $t_r \approx 102.5$ s, and after little decrement to 322.6 K levels off, what obviously affects the deformation of the concentration profiles of both solutes, however these changes are relatively less pronounced when comparing to the ideal adiabatic case. The mass overload, resulting from the high initial concentration of solutes and injection time, has a much greater effect on the deformation and tailing of the triangular concentration peaks.

Summarizing, the presence of column walls in theoretical models enabling predicting the course of chromatographic separation is indispensable. Only a precise mathematical model, including heat and mass transport phenomena in the chromatographic system, will allow for performing and optimizing the separation of solutes featuring pronounced values of adsorption enthalpy.

5. Conclusions

The development of modern chromatographic techniques is inextricably linked to the demand for precise mathematical models that enable fast and effective control of chromatographic separation processes. This is particularly important when the chromatographic process is no longer treated as isothermal, which is, among others, the result of reducing column packing particle size and column diameters as well. Mathematical models describing the processes occurring in the chromatographic column are becoming more and more complex, requiring advanced numerical methods that are increasingly faster and more accurate. In the Introduction section a number of works in which excellent and effective numerical techniques were described are mentioned. However, we noticed that in

many approaches the presence of column walls as important physical objects participating in heat transport phenomena is not always considered. In terms of volume fraction, they constitute a significant part of the column, exceeding 90% by volume (92.6% for a column 2.1 mm ID and 8 mm OD), and even more when taking into account the presence of connecting heads. Therefore, the column walls should not be neglected in predicting the results of chromatographic processes, especially in the cases **(a - c)** mentioned in the introduction. In this work, a mathematical model is presented that takes into account the presence of real chromatographic column walls made of real construction materials, and then a series of solutions are obtained for several different cases of column operation in order to determine the significance of the column wall presence issue. Based on the conducted research, the following should be stated:

- Due to minor thermal effects in the case of analytical columns with an internal diameter of 2.1 mm, operating under analytical conditions of low concentrations, the actual column model can be successfully replaced by a theoretical model of an adiabatic column without walls, and neglecting the presence of walls would not bring about serious errors. However, it should be remembered that in the case of a large pressure drop, not taking the wall into account will also result in larger errors;
- With the increased inlet concentration of levels typical for preparative conditions the presence of walls cannot be neglected in the creation and application of a mathematical model of the chromatographic separation process, even in the case of small, 2.1 mm columns. Moreover, the higher the concentration values and the higher the adsorption enthalpy values, the greater the discrepancies to be expected between a column operating under ideal adiabatic conditions and a real column equipped with physical external walls;
- In the case of preparative conditions, it is definitely recommended to consider the column walls presence in a robust mathematical model. The model should incorporate crucial thermal parameters of the material structuring the walls and the appropriate heat dissipation mechanism, especially in the highly exothermic adsorption process cases.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marcin Chutkowski: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing – original draft preparation, Writing – review and editing, Visualization, Project administration

Krzysztof Kaczmarek: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing – original draft preparation, Writing – review and editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Project administration

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